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Eukaryotic MAGs from the NEREA observatory: expanding the coastal microbiome dataset

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Abstract

Marine ecosystems are hotspots of biodiversity and biogeochemical activity, yet much of their complexity remains largely inaccessible without genome-resolved data. Here we present a curated dataset of 52 eukaryotic metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) reconstructed from samples collected between April 2019 and January 2020 at three NEREA (Naples Ecological REsearch for Augmented observatories) sites in the Gulf of Naples. NEREA is a coastal observatory integrating physical, chemical and biological measurements with state-of-the-art metagenomics. The eukaryotic MAGs have an average completeness of ~55% and genome size of ~20 Mb. Predicted proteins were functionally annotated against UniProtKB, InterPro, and eggNOG databases, and each MAG was taxonomically classified using a curated RNA polymerase A reference dataset. The recovered MAGs encompass diverse eukaryotic lineages, primarily Ochrophyta, Chlorophyta and Haptophyta. Building on the Tara Oceans eukaryotic MAG legacy, this release represents the first reconstruction of eukaryotic MAGs from a coastal time series, enabling temporal and functional analyses of eukaryotic plankton.

Background & Summary

The NEREA (Naples Ecological REsearch for Augmented observatories) initiative captures marine microbial dynamics in the Gulf of Naples through repeated sampling using an integrative multi-omics strategy¹. Drawing on the conceptual and methodological framework of the Tara Oceans expedition and the legacy of the Long Term Ecological Research Station-MareChiara (LTER-MC, <https://deims.org/0b87459a-da3c-45af-a3e1-cb1508519411>), NEREA aims to track temporal and spatial plankton dynamics, including targeted observations of key physico-chemical and biological processes. The focus is the Gulf of Naples (Figure 1), a coastal area under strong and variable anthropogenic pressure from industrial, agricultural, transportation and eutrophication activities and also under rapid climate-change-driven alterations²⁻⁴.

Figure 1 - Map showing the three NEREA sampling stations: LTER-MC (Long-Term Ecological Research site MareChiara), NRS (Sarno river mouth), and NRC (Dohrn Canyon). Reused from¹.

The plankton of the Gulf of Naples and related hydrological parameters have been sampled since 1984 in the framework of the LTER-MC⁵. NEREA extends these long-term observations by integrating deep expertise in physics and oceanography, analytical chemistry (nutrients, particulate and dissolved organic matter, lipid-derived oxylipins), stable-isotope analyses (carbon and nitrogen), quantitative microscopy and flow cytometry, high-throughput metabarcoding, shotgun metagenomics, and metatranscriptomics.

MAGs enable the recovery of partial to near-complete genomes directly from environmental DNA. Unlike single-gene surveys, MAGs provide genomic context for genes belonging to the same organism, enabling a genome-wide exploration of metabolic potential.

However, reconstructing eukaryotic MAGs presents several challenges; large genome sizes, introns, repetitive elements, polyploidy, and organellar sequences complicate assembly, binning and contamination removal workflows⁶. Although pioneering efforts have recovered hundreds of marine eukaryotic MAGs, often supplemented by single-cell amplified genomes, these typically focus on high-diversity pelagic systems^{7,8}. By employing co-assembly across multiple samples, automated binning coupled with rigorous manual curation, we here release 52 coastal eukaryotic MAGs, taxonomically classified across major lineages. Gene prediction was performed using the MarFERRerT database⁹; functional annotation was then conducted in parallel using multiple reference databases - UniProtKB¹⁰, eggNOG v5¹¹, and InterPro¹² - and the results were merged to generate a non-redundant set of annotations. This collection not only enriches the global repository of marine eukaryotic MAGs, but also complements the 3,818 prokaryotic MAGs, the prokaryotic gene catalogue, the metabarcoding, environmental and biodiversity data released in¹, therefore expanding the genomic and ecological context for integrative analyses of microbial community structure, function, and evolutionary dynamics in Mediterranean coastal systems.

Methods

From sampling to sequencing

Marine plankton samples were collected at three sites in the Gulf of Naples, at multiple depths and size fractions (0.22–3 μm , 3–20 μm , 20–200 μm , and 200–2000 μm), using a combination of plankton nets and Niskin bottles, with subsequent size-fractionation filtering using polycarbonate filters, following protocols adapted from the Tara Oceans expedition¹³, as detailed in¹. In total, 59 metagenomic samples were used. Sampling depth varied among sites, spanning from surface to deep layers (up to ~800 m), depending on hydrographic conditions. DNA was co-extracted with RNA from cryogenically-ground filters using Macherey-Nagel NucleoSpin kits, quantified

fluorometrically, fragmented, and subsequently prepared into metagenomic libraries. Libraries underwent end-repair, adenylation, barcode ligation, and PCR amplification before sequencing on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform (paired-end, 150 bp). Full methodological details of sampling, nucleic acid extraction, and library preparation are described in¹. Sequencing data were processed following standard quality control procedures, including adapter removal, trimming of low-quality bases, and removal of sequencing artefacts, as described in¹⁴.

From co-assembly to automatic binning

To reconstruct metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs), we first performed a co-assembly of 59 metagenomic samples from¹, belonging to different size classes (0.22–3 μm , $n = 17$; 3–20 μm , $n = 15$; 20–200 μm , $n = 16$; 200–2000 μm , $n = 11$). The co-assembly was performed using MEGAHIT¹⁵ v.2.1.9 with k-mer lengths of 41, 61, 81, 101, and 121 (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Schematic representation of the assembly, binning, and annotation pipelines used to generate the NEREA_MAGs_Euk_v1 dataset. Raw metagenomic reads from the NEREA project were co-assembled and binned into 52 eukaryotic MAGs. MAGs were then assigned to taxonomy and their proteins were predicted and functionally annotated through comparison with curated databases.

Co-assembly was selected to ensure sufficient sequencing depth for the reconstruction of large eukaryotic genomes, an approach shown to be effective for the Tara Oceans data⁷. Single-sample assemblies remain informative for resolving sample-specific genomic features, and metagenomic reads can be mapped (i.e., aligned) back to contigs from these assemblies to estimate coverage across samples. However, co-assembly increases the cumulative coverage of shared genomes across samples and is therefore better suited for the recovery of eukaryotic MAGs.

The number of reads used for the co-assembly ranged from 164,100,890 to 390,363,264 per sample, reported as the sum of forward and reverse reads (R1+R2) (total: 16,408,498,872 reads; Table S2). After assembly, the generated contigs underwent reformatting using *anvi'o* v.8¹⁶ (*anvi-script-reformat-fasta*) to simplify sequence headers and to remove contigs shorter than 2500 nucleotides, resulting in a refined contig file (*NEREA_final.contigs.2500.fna*).

Reads from individual samples were mapped back to the contigs using the BWA-MEM2 algorithm, employing a minimum percent identity threshold of 95%, as in¹³. The resulting alignments were sorted and indexed using *SAMtools*¹⁷. Mapping efficiency averaged around 20% per sample (Table S2), primarily due to the focus on larger contigs ($\geq 2,500$ nt). We then generated sample-specific contig profiles using *anvi'o* (*anvi-profile*) from the mapped BAM files, capturing coverage and single-nucleotide variant (SNV) information per contig. Each BAM file was first processed (*anvi-init-bam*) to meet *anvi'o* requirements. Individual profiles were subsequently merged (*anvi-merge*) into a combined dataset to leverage differential coverage information across samples.

A contig database (*NEREA_final-contigs.2500.db*) was created using *anvi'o* (*anvi-gen-contigs-database*), storing information such as k-mer frequencies and preliminary gene calls used for downstream binning. Genes within contigs were initially predicted using *Prodigal*¹⁸. Although read mapping and binning operate at the contig level, gene prediction is required within the *anvi'o* framework to identify single-copy core genes and other functional signals that are then used to estimate completeness, redundancy, and taxonomic affiliation during manual binning and curation. As *anvi'o* was originally developed for prokaryotic genome analysis, this step was used exclusively to support contig binning within our mixed (prokaryotic and eukaryotic) assembly. Subsequent gene prediction and functional annotation of eukaryotic MAGs were then performed using dedicated approaches tailored to eukaryotic genomes. To facilitate taxonomy assignment, we used hidden Markov models (HMMs), implemented in *anvi'o* (*anvi-run-hmms*), to identify single-copy core genes (SCGs) across the assembled contigs. These markers included standard bacterial, archaeal and eukaryotic SCGs together with additional universal markers targeting broader phylogenetic diversity, specifically the DNA-dependent RNA polymerase subunit genes¹⁹.

This search enriched the contigs database with phylogenetically informative marker gene occurrences.

To delineate potential genomes, we employed automatic binning via the CONCOCT²⁰ algorithm (anvi-cluster-contigs), which clusters contigs based on sequence composition and differential coverage across samples (Figure 2). Following the Tara Oceans eukaryotic MAGs approach⁷, we constrained CONCOCT to generate 300 clusters, a number intentionally set well below the expected total number of genomes in the assembly (across all domains of life) in order to minimize fragmentation of individual genomes. This under-clustering strategy results in broad initial clusters (“metabins”), which may include contigs from multiple organisms. These metabins were subsequently subjected to manual binning and curation within the anvi'o interactive interface to resolve individual eukaryotic MAGs.

Manual binning, MAG curation and taxonomic annotation

We used the RNA polymerase subunit A (RNAPolA) marker genes previously identified on the assembled contigs to assess the taxonomic affiliation of the 300 metabins. RNAPolA sequences retrieved from these metabins were aligned with DIAMOND v.2²¹ against a curated reference database of taxonomically annotated RNAPolA sequences²². Based on the taxonomic affiliation of these marker genes, 104 metabins showed a clear eukaryotic signal and were subsequently inspected in anvi'o for the manual extraction and curation of individual eukaryotic MAGs. Completeness and redundancy values were estimated in anvi'o using a set of eukaryotic single-copy core genes (SCGs) derived from BUSCO¹⁶. Specifically, completeness was calculated based on the BUSCO_83_Protista marker set available in anvi'o, as the percentage of the 83 protist SCGs detected at least once within a MAG. Redundancy was reported from the same SCGs set as the percentage of markers detected in more than one copy within a MAG, and was used as a proxy for potential contamination or mixed bins. Only MAGs with a minimum completeness of 25% were retained. Redundancy was controlled to maintain an acceptable balance with completeness, with a maximum tolerated value of approximately 12%. As a result, a total of 52 eukaryotic MAGs were recovered from the selected eukaryotic metabins (Figure 2) and their quality features are reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Distribution of assembly and quality metrics across NEREA eukaryotic MAGs. Each boxplot represents the variability of total length (bp), contig number, N50 (bp), GC content, completeness (%), and redundancy (%), highlighting overall assembly consistency and outlier genomes.

Taxonomic annotation of the final set of eukaryotic MAGs was refined by aligning their RNA polymerase subunit A (RNAPolA) sequences against the curated RNAPolA reference database using DIAMOND. In contrast to the initial annotation step, which was based on RNAPolA markers retrieved from metabins that could still contain multiple genomes, the second round of annotation was performed on manually curated MAGs and therefore yielded a more robust taxonomic assessment. Taxonomic assignment was based on the best DIAMOND hit to the curated RNAPolA reference database, using the following percent identity thresholds: $\geq 80\%$ for genus, 65–80% for family, 50–65% for order, and $< 50\%$ for class. Even when identity exceeded 95%, assignments were conservatively limited to the genus level. When the identity threshold supported a given rank but the best-matching reference sequence was annotated only at a higher taxonomic level, we conservatively retained the highest rank available in the reference database. One MAG (NR_Euk_v1_017) showed only 34% identity to the closest reference sequence and was therefore classified as unknown, although its eukaryotic origin was supported by the marker-gene evidence (Table S1).

The dataset includes representatives of major phyla such as Ochrophyta, Chlorophyta, Arthropoda, Haptophyta, Chordata, MAST, Cercozoa, Cryptophyta and Dinoflagellata, encompassing most dominant microbial eukaryotic groups in marine ecosystems (Table 1). Read mapping across size-fractionated metagenomic samples further showed that different taxonomic classes were preferentially represented in different size fractions, as reflected by the fraction in which MAGs from each class reached their highest average coverage (Table 1; Table S2). These patterns were broadly consistent with the expected size distribution of the corresponding taxa, with several diatom and metazoan classes showing highest coverage in the 20-200 μ m fraction, while smaller pico- and nanoeukaryotic groups were more strongly represented in the 0.22-3 μ m or 3-20 μ m. A small number of MAGs were additionally assigned to metazoan lineages (e.g., zooplankton taxa), reflecting the inclusion of planktonic life stages captured during sampling and are retained to provide a comprehensive representation of the planktonic community.

Phylum	Class	Number of MAGs	Representative size fraction
Ochrophyta	Mediophyceae	13	20-200 μ m
Ochrophyta	Chrysophyceae	6	0.22-3 μ m
Ochrophyta	Bacillariophyceae	3	20 -200 μ m
Ochrophyta	Pelagophyceae	3	3 -20 μ m
Ochrophyta	Dictyochophyceae	2	3 -20 μ m
Ochrophyta	Bolidophyceae	1	0.22 -3 μ m
Chlorophyta	Mamiellophyceae	7	3 - 20 μ m
Chlorophyta	Chloropicophyceae	2	20 - 200 μ m
Haptophyta	Prymnesiophyceae	3	3 - 20 μ m
Arthropoda	Hexanauplia	3	20 - 200 μ m
Chordata	Appendicularia	3	20 - 200 μ m
MAST	MAST-7	2	3 - 20 μ m
MAST	MAST-4-Clade-A	1	3 - 20 μ m
Cercozoa	Chlorarachniophyceae	1	0.22 - 3 μ m
Cryptophyta	Cryptophyceae	1	3 - 20 μ m
Dinoflagellata	Dinophyceae	1	3 - 20 μ m

Table 1 - Distribution of MAGs across eukaryotic classes and corresponding phyla in the NEREA eukaryotic MAG collection. The representative size fraction indicates the size fraction in which MAGs from each class reached their highest average coverage.

Protein prediction and functional annotation

To determine the most suitable reference database for gene prediction, we applied the easy-predict module of MetaEuk v.7²³ to the four NEREA MAGs with the highest completeness based on the BUSCO_83_Protista marker set (NR_Euk_v1_025: *Micromonas*, NR_Euk_v1_034: *Chaetoceros*, NR_Euk_v1_050: *Pseudo-nitzschia*, NR_Euk_v1_052: *Ostreococcus*). Protein predictions were conducted using multiple reference databases, including UniProtKB and SwissProt v.2025_03¹⁰, NCBI NR v.2025_03²⁴, EukProt v.3²⁵, and MarFERReT⁹. Among these, MarFERReT consistently produced the highest number of predicted proteins. Based on this comparative analysis and its relevance as a marine-focused resource, MarFERReT was selected as the optimal reference database for final gene prediction across all NEREA MAGs.

Functional annotation of predicted protein sequences was performed using three complementary approaches: (i) direct sequence similarity searches against the UniProtKB database were conducted using DIAMOND, providing protein-level functional descriptions based on the best hit for each query; (ii) orthology- and functional categorised annotations were assigned using eggNOG-mapper v.2²⁶ with the eggNOG v.5.0.2¹¹ database, yielding orthologous groups, COG functional categories, Gene Ontology (GO) terms, and KEGG Orthology (KO) identifiers; (iii) domain- and family-level functional annotation was performed using InterProScan v.5.74-105²⁷, which identified conserved protein domains, families, and functional sites based on the integrated InterPro collection of protein signature databases, including Pfam and InterProID. The outputs from these approaches were merged based on the protein identifiers to generate a final comprehensive annotation table in TSV format for each MAG, providing a complete list of functional assignments. Proteins with multiple annotations were consolidated by retaining only the best hit (lowest e-value) per gene. The resulting dataset was classified into three major categories based on annotation content: “Uncharacterized and Unnamed” proteins lacking informative functional or family description; “- like” proteins with weak or tentative homology to known sequences; “assigned” proteins with clearly defined and confidently attributed functions (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Stacked bar plots showing the relative composition of protein annotations across 52 eukaryotic MAGs based on best e-value hits. Each bar represents one MAG, displaying the proportion of “Assigned” (light blue), “-like” (gray), and “Uncharacterized and Unnamed” (black) proteins. Percentages are calculated over the total number of unique genes retained after filtering.

Data Records

Nucleotide FASTA files for the 52 MAGs generated in this study are available in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) under BioProject²⁸ (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB98715>), within the umbrella project NEREA Augmented Observatory. The co-assembly FASTA file from which the MAGs were extracted is available in Zenodo²² (<https://zenodo.org/records/20327956>), together with a text file describing the analysis pipeline, the script used for read mapping, the RNAPolA FASTA sequences with their associated metadata, and the supplementary tables. Predicted protein sequences for the 52 eukaryotic MAGs have been deposited in Zenodo²⁹ (<https://zenodo.org/records/1737624>) as amino acidic FASTA files, while the merged functional annotations of the corresponding predicted proteomes are available in a separate Zenodo record³⁰ (<https://zenodo.org/records/17403867>) as 52 individual tables.

Technical Validation

Quality validation of the genomic resources released in this Data Descriptor focused on the computational workflow used to generate the NEREA co-assembly and eukaryotic MAGs. High-resolution coverage profiles were computed across all metagenomes included in the co-assembly and used in combination with automatic binning. Each resulting bin was then manually inspected and refined to enable the resolution of composite bins and the removal of potential contaminants. Taxonomic assignments were validated by cross-referencing phylogenetic marker genes and DIAMOND-based similarity searches against curated marine reference databases. For gene prediction, we benchmarked MetaEuk results obtained using multiple reference databases (UniProtKB, SwissProt, NCBI NR, EukProt, and MarFERReT) on the four most complete NEREA MAGs. Taken together, these procedures ensure that the co-assembly and MAGs released here constitute high-quality, well-validated genomic resources suitable for downstream ecological and evolutionary analyses.

Usage Notes

The eukaryotic MAGs and co-assembly released here can be directly integrated into comparative genomics, functional profiling, and metatranscriptomic recruitment analyses. Their compatibility with the broader NEREA multi-omics framework, which includes environmental parameters, microscopy, flow cytometry, metabarcoding, and prokaryotic MAG datasets published in¹, enables cross-layer investigations of plankton diversity and ecosystem dynamics. As with any metagenome-derived resource, MAGs may underrepresent low-abundance or highly fragmented genomes, and co-assembly strategies can smooth strain-level diversity. These aspects should be considered when interpreting fine-scale ecological patterns. The NEREA observatory is ongoing, and future data releases will expand the genomic catalogue and incorporate metatranscriptomic datasets, facilitating the study of gene expression dynamics and seasonal processes at higher resolution.

Data Availability

All data described in this study are publicly available. Reconstructed MAGs have been deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) PRJEB98715. Additional derived datasets are available through Zenodo, including the co-assembly summary and MAG taxonomic overview (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.20327956>), predicted protein sequences (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17376243>), and functional annotations of the predicted proteomes (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.17403867>).

Code Availability

The code and command-line workflow used in this study are available at²². The repository includes `pipeline_nerea_mags.txt`, a text file documenting the commands and analysis steps used to generate the MAG catalog, together with the `map.sh` script used for read mapping.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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